

Evaluation of Mechanical Properties of Al6061 Composite by Stir Casting Method

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Abstract: Aluminium alloy-based metallic matrix composites (MMC) have recently gained popularity in various aerospace and automotive applications. Aluminium has been utilized as a matrix material due to its high mechanical qualities, superior formability, and diverse industrial applications. The Al6061 alloy system becomes harder, stronger in tension, and more wear-resistant when TiB₂-SiC-Rh is added as reinforcement. Al6061-TiB₂-SiC-Rh composites were created in this study using a liquid metallurgical method, with TiB₂-SiC-Rh added in percentages ranging from 2% to 8% by weight in increments of 2%. The cast matrix alloy and its composites were treated with solutionizing at 500°C for 1 hour before being quenched in different media like air, water, and oil. After quenching, the samples were aged both artificially and naturally. Microstructural analysis was conducted to understand the relationship between structure and mechanical properties. Mechanical characteristics, including microhardness and abrasive wear experiments, were performed on matrix Al6061 and Al6061-TiB₂-SiC-Rh composites before and after heat treatment. Under the same heat treatment conditions, the Al6061-TiB₂-SiC-Rh composites exhibited improved microhardness, tensile strength, and reduced wear compared with the Al matrix alloy.

Keywords: Al6061, Al6061-TiB₂-SiC-Rh, Heat Treatment, Metallic Matrix Composites, Stir Casting.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites are engineered materials made up of several distinct phases that are in close proximity to one another and have a discernible interface. The type of matrix material and the type of reinforcement are the two primary classification levels for composites. For example, if the matrix material is primarily polymer-based, the composite is called a polymer matrix composite (PMC). Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) include small fibers or whiskers interwoven with a ceramic matrix, such as those made of materials like TiB₂, SiC, or Rh. Metal matrix composites (MMCs), developed in the early 1960s, consist of a metallic matrix reinforced with ceramic materials, offering improved mechanical properties compared to pure metals. The metallic matrix in MMCs is often strengthened using ceramic reinforcements, which significantly enhance properties such as strength, stiffness, and wear resistance [1].

Aluminium-based metal matrix composites (MMCs) have attracted significant attention due to their lightweight nature, high strength-to-weight ratio, and superior thermal and mechanical properties. Al6061, in particular, is a widely used aluminium alloy in the aerospace, automotive, and structural sectors because of its excellent machinability, weldability, and corrosion resistance [2]. However, by reinforcing Al6061 with ceramic particulates like TiB₂ and SiC, further improvements can be made in key areas such as tensile strength, wear resistance, and hardness, making the composite material more suitable for demanding applications where enhanced mechanical performance is crucial.

The stir casting method is one of the most efficient and cost-effective liquid metallurgy techniques for fabricating metal matrix composites [3]. By using this process, uniform distribution of the reinforcing particles can be achieved in the molten metal, ensuring homogeneity in the composite structure. This study selected TiB₂, SiC, and Rh as reinforcements for the Al6061 matrix. When added in specific weight percentages, these reinforcements are expected to significantly improve the mechanical properties, such as hardness, tensile strength, and wear resistance, of the base Al6061 alloy. This research aims to explore the effect of different weight fractions of TiB₂-SiC-Rh on the mechanical properties of the Al6061 composite and to investigate the potential of this material for advanced industrial applications [4].

2 BACKGROUND

The study conducted by Anand Kumar et al. on improving the mechanical characteristics of aluminium matrix composites through the addition of reinforcements such as TiC, silicon carbide, Al₂O₃, TiO₂, and Tin is well recognized [5]. The in-situ approach is strongly preferred over conventional ex-situ methods for reinforcing the aluminium matrix with ceramic phases, such as titanium carbide (TiC). The Al-Cu alloy (Al2014) was used as the matrix in this study, and TiC was reinforced using an in-situ method [6].

Compared to the Al-4.5% Cu alloy, the metal matrix composite (MMC) alloy Al-5% Cu/10% TiC exhibited higher yield strength, ultimate tensile strength, and hardness. According to reports, the percentage increases in yield strength and ultimate tensile strength were approximately 15% and 24%, respectively.

The microstructures and mechanical characteristics of organically aged, equal-channel angular pressing (ECAP)-treated, ultrafine-grained (UFG), and coarsely grained (CG) Al6061 alloys, and their changes after heat treatment were examined by Zhao et al. Their research showed that the natural aging, tensile yield strength, ultimate tensile strength, and microhardness of UFG specimens were 103%, 35%, and 48% higher than those of the CG samples. The study demonstrated that extreme plastic deformation significantly enhances the mechanical properties of age-hardened aluminium alloys.

Investigations were carried out with the Al6061-TiB₂-SiC-Rh in-situ composite using readily available Al-10% Ti and Al-3% Br master alloys produced through the stir casting method [7]-[9]. Microstructure analysis, microhardness testing, grain size studies, and tensile testing were performed on the matrix and composite alloys. TiB₂-SiC-Rh particles were uniformly distributed within the matrix, as observed in the microstructure analysis. The composite material exhibited a smaller average grain size than the unreinforced alloy. In addition, the Al6061-TiB₂-SiC-Rh composite showed significantly higher microhardness, yield strength, and ultimate tensile strength than the unreinforced Al6061 alloy.

3 FABRICATION

3.1 Methodology

Stir casting is a widely used technique for producing metal matrix composites (MMCs) by incorporating reinforcements into a molten metal matrix. The process involves creating a vortex within the molten metal using a mechanical stirrer to ensure a uniform distribution of reinforcement particles. A bottom-pouring furnace is an efficient choice for stir casting, as it uses an automated pouring system to instantly transfer the melt mixture (matrix and reinforcement) into molds. During the stir-casting process, a mechanical mixer connected to a variable-speed motor controls the stirrer's speed, allowing for precise control of the vortex and enhancing particle dispersion within the matrix [10]-[12].

3.2 Materials

The primary alloying elements in Aluminium 6061 are silicon and magnesium. Its designation in the Unified Numbering Systems (UNS) is A96061. This aluminium alloy is precipitation-hardened and was originally introduced in 1935 under the name "Alloy 61S." Al6061 is highly popular for its excellent mechanical properties, second only to Al6063 in terms of general use. It exhibits good machinability, weldability, and formability, with an outstanding strength-to-weight ratio, which makes it a highly sought-after material in the automotive, aerospace, and defense industries. Its low specific weight and high fatigue resistance further contribute to its selection as a matrix material for composites.

TiB₂ is a widely used ceramic reinforcement in metal matrix composites due to its high hardness, strength-to-density ratio, and excellent wear resistance. It also has a relatively high melting point, which makes it ideal for high-temperature applications. Silicon carbide (SiC) and Rh particles are also commonly used for their exceptional mechanical properties, further enhancing the composite's performance. The materials are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Materials

3.3 Stir Casting Procedure

In the stir-casting process, the molten aluminium matrix is stirred continuously to ensure uniform dispersion of reinforcement particles within the melt. However, exposure of the melt to the environment during stirring can lead to surface oxidation, reducing the wettability of the aluminium and preventing proper integration of the reinforcement particles. To mitigate this, proper control of stirring speed and temperature is critical. Once the matrix and reinforcements are mixed uniformly, the molten composite is poured into molds to form the final specimen. Stir-casting machine and the prepared specimen are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively.

Fig. 2 Testing on a Stir casting Machine

Fig. 3 Specimen

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Hardness

Hardness is a material's ability to resist deformation under applied force. It reflects the material's resistance to abrasion, wear, and scratching. The Vickers Hardness Test was used to determine the hardness values of the Al6061-based composites. The compositions are given in Table 1. For convenience, denote the compositions with C1, C2, C3, and C4.

Table 1. List of Compositions

S.No.	Composition	Notation
1	Al6061+1.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	C1
2	Al6061+3.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	C2
3	Al6061+5.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	C3
4	Al6061+7.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	C4

For convenience, the composites are denoted as Composition-1, composition-2, etc. The hardness values increase with the percentage of reinforcement due to the high hardness of the reinforcing materials. The hardness follows the law of mixtures, with a limit at which further reinforcement may not yield significant improvements. The hardness values are given in Table 2. Fig. 4 plots the VHN values of the four composites.

Table 2. Hardness Values

Compositions	Trail 1			Trail 2			Avg. VHN
	D1	D2	VHN	D1	D2	VHN	
Al6061+1.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	87	78	167	57	85	164	165.5
Al6061+3.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	79	97	172	79	97	174	173
Al6061+5.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	79	97	178	67	68	176	177
Al6061+7.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	80	89	185	68	89	190	187.5

Fig. 4 VHN values of the four composites

4.2 Heat Treating

Heat treatment involves heating the material to its recrystallization temperature and quenching it in different media, such as water or oil. Hardness values were measured after the quenching process. The results indicate that heat treatment enhances hardness, with oil quenching yielding higher values than water quenching. The experimental results of quenching by water and oil are given in Table 3 and Table 4, respectively.

Table 3. Heat treatment by water quenching

Compositions	Trail 1			Trail 2			Avg. VHN
	D1	D2	VHN	D1	D2	VHN	
Al6061+1.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	98	98	172	86	87	178	175
Al6061+3.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	68	98	182	87	84	186	184
Al6061+5.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	68	96	190	88	87	196	193
Al6061+7.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	68	95	202	93	97	208	205

Table 4. Heat treatment by oil Quenching

Compositions	Trail 1			Trail 2			Avg. VHN
	D1	D2	VHN	D1	D2	VHN	
Al6061+1.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	76	86	187	78	82	189	188
Al6061+3.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	67	78	196	79	87	197	196.5
Al6061+5.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	66	78	202	77	92	206	204
Al6061+7.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	78	87	210	70	94	216	213

The oil-quenching process improved hardness by approximately 30% compared to water-quenching. This is attributed to the quenching media's different cooling rates and equilibrium conditions. Fig. 5 displays the VHN with water and oil quenching.

Fig. 5 Heat transfer VHN by water and oil quenching

4.3 Wear Resistance

Wear resistance is the ability of a material to withstand surface damage caused by mechanical action, such as abrasion or impact. The wear tests were conducted at different distances. The wear test specimen and wear test machine are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 Wear Test sample and Wear Test Machine

The experimental results of wear resistance for different distances are given in Tables 5 to 7. The loss of weight is plotted in Fig. 7.

Table 5. Wear at 1kg load - 200m

S. No.	Material	Initial weight	Final weight	Loss of weight
1	Al6061+1.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	15.674	14.241	1.433
2	Al6061+3.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	15.690	14.345	1.345
3	Al6061+5.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	14.789	13.555	1.234
4	Al6061+7.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	14.345	13.222	1.123

Table 6. Wear at 1kg load - 400m

S. No.	Material	Initial weight	Final weight	Loss of weight
1	Al6061+1.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	14.551	12.206	2.345
2	Al6061+3.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	14.456	11.999	2.457
3	Al6061+5.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	13.444	10.765	2.679
4	Al6061+7.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	12.912	10.036	2.876

Table 7. Wear at 1kg load - 600m

S. No.	Material	Initial weight	Final weight	Loss of weight
1	Al6061+1.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	12.206	8.639	3.567
2	Al6061+3.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	11.999	8.541	3.458
3	Al6061+5.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	10.765	7.628	3.137
4	Al6061+7.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	10.036	6.909	3.127

As the reinforcement percentage increased, the material's wear resistance improved significantly. Higher reinforcement percentages showed better performance under increased distances and load conditions.

Fig. 7 Wear Resistance

4.4 Corrosion

Corrosion resistance tests were conducted to measure weight loss in corrosive environments. Table 8 presents the corrosion values obtained in the test, and Fig. 8 plots weight loss with corrosion.

Table 8. Corrosion Values

S.no	Material	Initial weight	Final weight	Loss of weight
1	Al6061+1.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC +1.8% Rh	3.785	3.031	0.754
2	Al6061+3.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	2.875	2.201	0.674
3	Al6061+5.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	2.89	2.327	0.563
4	Al6061+7.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	3.56	3.239	0.321

Reinforced composites displayed superior corrosion resistance, with a weight loss reduction as the reinforcement percentage increased.

Fig. 8. Loss of Weight with Corrosion

4.5 Compression

Compression tests were conducted to measure the material's ability to withstand compressive forces. The failure load values obtained are given in Table 9. Fig. 9 plots the failure load.

Table 9. Compression Test Values

S. No.	Material	Failure load KN
1	Al6061+1.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	190
2	Al6061+3.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	197
3	Al6061+5.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	205
4	Al6061+7.2% TiB ₂ -SiC-Rh+2%SiC+1.8% Rh	210

Fig. 9. Failure load with compression

The compressive strength of the composites improved with the increasing weight percentage of reinforcements. This indicates that the material's ability to resist compressive forces was enhanced.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Stir casting was used to create the Al6061-TiB₂-SiC-Rh nano matrix composite materials, which were then extruded. The alloy structure showed a uniform distribution of the nano TiB₂-SiC-Rh particles. The nanocomposite material Al6061-TiB₂-SiC-Rh exhibited higher microhardness than the base matrix material. Adding 2% weight of TiB₂-SiC-Rh nanoparticles to the Al6061 matrix alloy resulted in a 12.2% improvement in microhardness. Adding these nanoparticles considerably increased the final tensile strength and yield strength of the Al6061-TiB₂-SiC-Rh (2% weight) nanocomposite. The 8% weight TiB₂-SiC-Rh nanocomposite reinforced Al6061 exhibited a 54.11% improvement in ultimate tensile strength compared to the LM13 alloy. However, the flexibility of the Al6061-TiB₂-SiC-Rh nanocomposite was reduced compared to the matrix alloy. Adding 2% weight of TiB₂-SiC-Rh nanoparticles reduced the ductility by 32.72%. The Al6061 matrix material with 8% weight reinforcement demonstrated a 40.32% improvement in compressive strength compared to the base Al6061 alloy. The fracture toughness of the matrix material also improved with the addition of reinforcement. Including 2% weight of TiB₂ nanoparticles in the Al6061 matrix increased the fracture toughness by 130%. As the weight percentage of reinforcement increased, so did the wear resistance. The wear resistance of the Al6061 alloy with 6% weight nano TiB₂ reinforcement showed a 40.76% improvement compared to the base Al6061 alloy. Compared to the as-cast Al6061 alloy, the wear resistance of the 6-hour heat-treated Al6061 alloy improved by 21.57% and by 14.28% in the extruded Al6061 alloy.

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ETHICS STATEMENT

This study did not involve human or animal subjects and, therefore, did not require ethical approval.

STATEMENT OF CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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